

Nsaid-Gastropathy in Patients with Rheumatologic Diseases

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One of the most critical issues in modern rheumatology is the gastroduodenal side effects associated with the use of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), which can lead to severe complications. NSAIDs most commonly have a damaging effect on the stomach and duodenum, a condition termed "NSAID-induced gastropathy" or "NSAID-gastroduodenopathy syndrome." "NSAID-gastropathy" was introduced in 1986 to distinguish specific gastric mucosal lesions associated with NSAID use from classic gastroduodenal ulcers.

NSAID-Gastropathy refers to erosive-ulcerative lesions in the gastro-duodenal area that arise from NSAID use, showing a characteristic clinical and endoscopic pattern. These lesions have distinct features: they are often multiple, show mild symptoms, and carry a high risk of gastrointestinal bleeding (GIB); there is a documented association with NSAID intake, with localization primarily in the antral part (less frequently in the body of the stomach and duodenum), absence of an inflammatory border around the ulcer; histological features include foveolar hyperplasia of the mucosa; and relatively rapid healing after NSAID discontinuation. The effects of aspirin and NSAIDs on the upper GI tract can lead to severe consequences, including bleeding and perforation, underscoring the surgical implications of this issue.

Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are the most commonly used medications in medical practice. Approximately 30 million people worldwide take these medications daily. Each year, around 500 million prescriptions for NSAIDs are issued. About 10-20% of individuals over 65 years old take or have taken NSAIDs. Self-administration of NSAIDs is seven times higher than what is recommended by physicians. The expected use of NSAIDs is likely to increase, associated with the rise of over-the-counter medications, an aging population, and the growing frequency of aspirin being prescribed as an antiplatelet agent. Erosions and ulcers of the gastric mucosa occur in 10-30% of individuals who take NSAIDs for an extended period. With prolonged (more than 6 weeks) use of NSAIDs, gastro- and duodenopathies develop in 70% of cases. Changes in the mucous membrane of the gastro-duodenal zone often have a recurrent nature, with minimal subjective sensations or a complete absence of clinical manifestations, which often leads to delayed consultations with a physician. In one-third of patients who take NSAIDs for a prolonged period and have no symptoms related to the gastro-duodenal zone (in 34% of cases), according to E.L. Nasonov and A.E. Karateev (2000), characteristic endoscopic signs of NSAID gastropathy are revealed during preventive esophagogastroduodenoscopy.

The significant increase in the consumption of NSAIDs has led to a rise in the frequency of systemic toxic effects, primarily associated with damage to the gastric mucosa and the mucosa of the duodenum. A distinctive feature of NSAID gastropathy is the involvement of the upper gastrointestinal tract and its development typically in elderly patients rather than in younger ones.

The primary mechanism of the therapeutic action of NSAIDs is associated with the interruption of the cyclooxygenase (COX) pathway in the metabolism of arachidonic acid, which leads to the suppression of prostaglandin synthesis—an essential product of inflammation. Currently, two forms of COX have been discovered and studied: constitutive (COX-1) and inducible (COX-2). COX-1 protects the gastrointestinal mucosa, while COX-2 is involved in the production of prostaglandins at the site of inflammation. The spectrum of primary physiological effects of prostaglandins includes the stimulation of protective bicarbonate and mucus secretion, enhancement of local blood flow in the mucosa, and activation of cell proliferation in normal regeneration processes [1]. The inhibition of COX-2 activity is what determines the anti-inflammatory effect. In the formation of both NSAID

gastropathy and gastro-duodenal peptic ulcers, significant importance is attributed to the disruption of the balance between aggressive factors and the protective mechanisms of the gastrointestinal mucosa, with NSAIDs affecting all levels of the intestinal barrier—pre-epithelial, epithelial, and post-epithelial [7, 8].

As etiopathogenetic factors in the development of NSAID gastropathy, the following factors are considered: local irritation of the gastric mucosa and subsequent ulcer formation; inhibition of the synthesis of prostaglandins (PG) (PGE2, PGI2) and their metabolites, prostacyclin and thromboxane A2, in the gastric mucosa, which perform a cytoprotective function; and disruption of blood flow in the mucosa against the background of prior endothelial damage to blood vessels after taking NSAIDs [14]. The topical damaging effect of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs manifests in that after some time following the administration of these drugs, an increase in the permeability of hydrogen and sodium ions into the mucosa is observed. NSAIDs suppress the production of prostaglandins not only at the sites of inflammation but also at the systemic level, so the development of gastropathy is a programmed pharmacological effect of these medications [11, 15].

It is suggested that non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) can induce apoptosis of epithelial cells through pro-inflammatory cytokines. The use of these drugs damages the hydrophobic layer on the surface of the gastric mucosa, depletes the composition of phospholipids, and reduces the secretion of components of gastric mucus. In the mechanism of the ulcerogenic action of NSAIDs, a vital role is played by the alteration of lipid peroxidation. The products formed from free radical oxidation lead to damage to the gastric mucosa and the breakdown of mucopolysaccharides. Additionally, NSAIDs have a specific effect on the synthesis of leukotrienes, and a decrease in their number results in a reduction of mucus that possesses cytoprotective properties. A decrease in the synthesis of prostaglandins leads to a reduction in the synthesis of mucus and bicarbonates, which are the primary protective barrier of the gastric mucosa against the aggressive factors of gastric juice [2, 6, 9].

When taking NSAIDs, the levels of prostacyclin and nitric oxide decrease, which adversely affects circulation in the submucosal layer of the gastrointestinal tract and creates an additional risk of damage to the gastric mucosa and the duodenum. Changes in the balance between protective and aggressive factors in the stomach lead to the formation of ulcers and the development of complications such as bleeding, perforation, and penetration [12, 13]. To date, the significance of *Helicobacter pylori* in the pathogenesis of NSAID gastropathy needs to be clarified. Apparently, infection with *H. pylori* increases the likelihood of developing NSAID-induced ulcers, erosions, and gastrointestinal bleeding [3].

The symptoms of the discussed pathology are well-known to clinicians. These include pain (more often in the epigastric region) associated with the intake of the medication (patients switch to taking it after meals to reduce discomfort), dyspeptic syndrome—feelings of heaviness after eating, a sense of rapid satiety, bloating in the epigastric area, and less frequently nausea and vomiting. The pain and dyspeptic syndromes are not characterized by seasonality, unlike "classical" gastro-duodenal ulcers [5]. Approximately 30-40% of examined patients undergoing prolonged (more than 6 weeks) NSAID therapy report symptoms of dyspepsia that do not correlate with the findings obtained during esophagogastroduodenoscopy. NSAID gastropathy typically develops within the first 1-3 months of starting treatment; therefore, patients who have just begun taking NSAIDs require increased attention from physicians for timely diagnosis of complications. The highest likelihood of developing erosive and ulcerative lesions is observed in the first month of NSAID use; thereafter, it decreases somewhat and remains stable over the following years of treatment.

In NSAID-induced gastropathy, the development of erosions (often multiple) or ulcers localized in the antral part of the stomach is typical. NSAID-induced ulcers are more often single, relatively small, and shallow; multiple ulcers, contrary to popular belief, are relatively rare. Individual pharmacodynamic characteristics of NSAIDs also play a role in the development of NSAID gastropathy. Drugs in this group exert different effects on the activity ratio of COX isoenzymes. According to this theory, the lower the concentration of the drug required to block COX-1 (i.e., the lower the selectivity of the drug

for COX-2), the more frequently it causes the development of gastro-duodenal complications. Data from meta-analyses of population studies show that the risk of developing gastro-duodenal complications decreases in the following order: indomethacin – piroxicam – naproxen – diclofenac – ibuprofen.

The potential development of NSAID gastropathy can be predicted by considering risk factors that have been identified by epidemiologists in the analysis of data obtained from retrospective studies of large groups of patients taking NSAIDs. The presence of such factors is associated with a significantly higher relative risk of developing severe gastro-duodenal complications at the population level. Among the most critical risk factors for NSAID-induced gastropathy are a history of ulcers and older age (over 65 years) of patients. Additional risk factors include concomitant use of anticoagulants and high doses of glucocorticoids, use of NSAIDs in high doses, simultaneous use of multiple different medications from this group, and severe comorbidities, primarily of the cardiovascular system [4].

The dose of the medication and the duration of treatment also affect the occurrence of NSAID gastropathy. For instance, in patients over 60 years old, the risk of developing gastropathy increases 2.8 times when doses exceeding standard levels by 1.5 times are prescribed, and it increases 8 times when the doses are tripled. At the same time, it has been established that erosive and ulcerative lesions of the stomach can occur even with treatment using low doses of acetylsalicylic acid (150–300 mg/day), which is often prescribed for the prevention of thrombosis in ischemic heart disease [10]. The use of selective COX-2 inhibitors reduces the risk of developing erosive and ulcerative lesions but does not entirely eliminate them.

Based on the pathogenesis, no significant correlation has been found between the route of administration of NSAIDs (oral, parenteral, or rectal) and the frequency of developing erosive and ulcerative lesions, as the primary ulcerogenic effect is due to the systemic toxic action of NSAIDs. Treating NSAID gastropathy presents a challenging task, as complete cessation of NSAIDs without prescribing acid-suppressive medications does not lead to healing of ulcers and erosions in 60% of patients within the next 1-3 months. The goals of therapy include alleviating clinical symptoms, epithelialization of mucosal defects, prevention of complications, prevention of recurrences, and improving the quality of life for patients.

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